

**Relationships between man and the mountain
environment in terms of geomorphological hazards
and human impact in Europe**

IAG SYMPOSIUM PROCEEDINGS
Dornbirn (Austria), 14 July 2002

Edited by Lisa BORGATTI and Mauro SOLDATI

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On the cover: Pfannensee in Silbertal with Patriol (photo by Richard Neyer)

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PROGRAMME OF THE SYMPOSIUM

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Mario PANIZZA on behalf of International Association of Geomorphologists

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Marie Louise HINTERAUER on behalf of the City Council of Dornbirn

INVITED LECTURES

Antonio CENDRERO (University of Cantabria, Spain)

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Berthold BAUER (University of Vienna, Austria)

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Jean-Claude FLAGEOLLET (CERG, Strasbourg, France)

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Fabio LUINO (National Research Council, Turin, Italy)

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Poster Session

Methodological approach for the EIA of geomorphologic assets; a case study in northern Spain

Jaime BONACHEA, Viola Maria BRUSCHI, Juan REMONDO and
Antonio CENDRERO

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This study includes the assessment of the impact on land units with high potential for use and land units of high productivity; it is an essential part of a methodological approach for the assessment of impacts on geomorphologic environment. The approach is based on the use of indicators of geomorphic effects and the criteria of performance or sustainability, as well as their translation into significant terms.

The methodology has been applied to an area in northern Spain where population density is quite high as well as human and industrial activities, comparing two alternatives for a new motorway crossing the area.

Basic information for these analyses was compiled and a complete database that was implemented through a Geographical Information System was created. This database includes information about altitude, slope gradient, solar radiation, population centres, road networks and the new motorway alternatives, geotechnical limitations, natural hazards, soil capability and land cover/vegetation.

Firstly, units of high potential for use and high productivity have been selected by means of integrating different thematic maps (slope gradient, geotechnical conditions, flood hazard, distance to population centres, distance to roads, and soil capability, altitude, solar radiation and vegetation, respectively).

In order to assess the geomorphological impact, the units of high potential for use and high productivity have been overlapped (GIS cross function) with the alternatives of the motorway. Thus, affected area and percentage of unit lost have been computed for each alternative; therefore, geomorphological impacts are expressed in those terms. Performance of the geomorphological impact has been assessed on the basis of percentage of unit type destroyed.

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Finally, the geomorphological impact should be expressed in significant terms that permit to understand the meaning of the impact and its comparison with others; according to this, final impacts have been expressed in monetary values.

The whole procedure is transparent and replicable and can easily be implemented on a GIS platform, thus enabling rapid analysis and comparison of alternatives, as well as the integration of the impacts analysed within a more general EIA.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR THE EIA OF GEOMORPHOLOGIC ASSETS; A CASE STUDY IN NORTHERN SPAIN

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INTRODUCTION

Linear structures produce a series of environmental impacts, directly or indirectly determined by geomorphologic characteristics (González Alonso, 1989; Cavallin et al., 1994). Assessment of those impacts can only be carried out if the different effects of specific human actions related to construction and operation of the structures are identified, measured and evaluated in terms that allow comparisons with each other and with environmental concerns existing in the region. Geomorphologic assets in this analysis include land units with high potential for use, high productivity or high value for conservation. Of particular interest is the development and testing of GIS procedures for the implementation of those schemes and their eventual incorporation into EIA practices.

STUDY AREA

The study area (Fig. 1) is part of the Deva valley, northern Spain (approximately 190 km² and 80,000 inhabitants). The climate is oceanic, mild and humid. Geomorphology is determined by V-shaped valleys with limited development of alluvial plains (Tamés et al., 1991). Land cover is intensely transformed; natural vegetation barely covers 16%, and only part of it are indigenous forests. Areas reforested with pine trees amount to about 60%. Built-up areas are concentrated on alluvial plain and adjacent slopes.

The project considered is a part of a motorway linking the towns of Vitoria-Gasteiz and Eibar. Environmental concerns related to geomorphologic characteristics are: a) land occupation or degradation in a valley where land with high potential for use is scarce; b) damage to areas of high natural value or productivity, in a zone where the extent of well-preserved natural ecosystems is limited; c) visual impact; d) interference with geomorphologic processes and potential hazard increase. Only the first two are dealt with here.

METHODOLOGY

Two alternative routes have been analysed (Fig. 1). Basic information for these analyses was compiled and a complete database that was implemented through a Geographical Information System (Ilwis 2.2) was created. This database includes information about altitude, slope gradient, solar radiation, population centres, geotechnical limitations, natural hazards, soil capability, land cover/vegetation, road network and the new motorway alternatives.

1. Firstly, units of high potential for use (UHPU) and high productivity or high value for conservation (UHVC/UHPP) were defined and mapped combining different thematic maps: slope gradient, geotechnical conditions, flood hazard, distance to population centres and distance to roads, in the case of UHPU (Fig. 2); soil capability, altitude, solar radiation and vegetation, were used to define UHVC/UHPP (Fig. 3). UHVC were derived directly from the land cover map (*Alnus* cospes and *Quercus* wood on acid terrain).

Fig. 1. Location of the study area and the new motorway alternatives.

Fig. 2. Thematic maps and criteria used to define UHPU.

Criteria to define units of high potential for use					
Class	Gradient (%)	Geotechnical conditions	Flood return period (y)	Distance to centres (m)	Distance to roads (m)
High	< 20	favourable, acceptable	> 1000	< 1000	< 200
Low	> 20	unfav., very unfav.	< 1000	> 1000	> 200

Two types of units were defined: High potential units and other units.

Fig. 3. Thematic maps and criteria used to define UHVC/UHPP.

Class	UHVC		UHPP	
	Land cover	Soil capability	Altitude (m)	Radiation (%)
High	<i>Alnus</i> , <i>Quercus</i>	A, B	< 300	30 (>179)
Low	Other	C, D, E	> 300	70 (<179)

2. In order to assess geomorphological impacts, the maps of high potential for use and high productivity or high value for conservation were overlapped (GIS cross function) with motorway alternatives. A road width of 100 m within which total loss is assumed was used. A buffer of 50 m on either side was also considered. Tunnel sectors were excluded from the analysis. Affected area and percentage of unit lost were computed for each alternative; therefore, geomorphological impacts are expressed in those terms. Performance of the alternatives on geomorphological terms has been assessed on the basis of percentage of unit type destroyed (Figs. 4, 5).

Fig. 4. UHPU: Area affected by motorway and economic impact in €/pixel (1pixel=100 m²). The results obtained show that alternative B has a lower impact.

Alternative A		UHPU		Alternative B	
(m ²)	% Total	Total area before motorway	(m ²)	% Total	
5,404,400	4.38		5,404,400	4.38	
97,600	1.81	Area affected	64,900	1.20	
48,800	0.90	Area in buffer	32,450	0.60	
43,920,000		Monetary value (€)	29,205,000		

Fig. 5. UHVC/UHPP: Area affected by motorway and economic impact in €/pixel (1pixel=100 m²). The results obtained show that alternative A has a lower impact.

Alternative A		UHVC/UHPP		Alternative B						
Sup. (m ²)	% total	% unit type	Prod./year	€/year	Units	Sup. (m ²)	% total	% unit type	Prod./year	€/year
81,600	0.06	1.22	20,4 m ³ /y	15,504	Valuable natural (UHVC)	143,000	0.12	2.14	37,5 m ³ /y	27,170
158,800	0.13	2.59	269.9 t/y	53,992	Productive managed (UHPP)	236,000	0.19	3.86	401.2 t/y	80,240

3. Geomorphological impacts have been expressed in significant terms that facilitate communication with non-experts and integration with other impacts. In the case of UHPU, translation into significant terms was made considering a reference value of 360 €/m², corresponding to a 2,000 m² plot, flat and hazard free, less than 100 m away from a road and 200 m from the town of Vergara; for UHPP, area affected was translated into annual crop value taking into account local productivity (Gobierno Vasco, 1999) and prices (about 3,400 €/ha/year); potential wood production was used in the case of UHVC (about 1,900 €/ha/year); this has the meaning of "minimum ecological loss" as the value of other environmental services has not been included.

CONCLUSIONS

The procedure described, based on the identification of landform units and materials, makes it possible to express impacts on geomorphological assets by means of simple, quantitative indicators. On the basis of those indicators criteria of sustainability and relevance can be defined, also in quantitative terms, to facilitate comparison and integration with other impacts. These, in turn, allow the identification of suitable mitigation or compensation measures. The whole procedure is transparent and replicable and can easily be implemented on a GIS platform, thus enabling rapid analysis and comparison of alternatives.

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A methodological approach to assess the impact of a motorway on visual landscape

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The introduction of new large structures such as a motorway represents a visual intrusion that may reduce visual quality (determined mainly on the bases of three groups of factors: geomorphology, vegetation, and land use). This reduction or “visual impact” is related, on the one hand to the degree of visibility of the new structure (magnitude) and, on the other hand, to the contrast between the structure and pre-existing landscape (intensity).

The analysis of visual impact has been based on the identification of integrated environmental units defined on the basis of geomorphology, land cover and human occupation. The intrinsic visual quality of those units has been determined according to categories of visual quality defined for geomorphology and land use-cover units, separately. To obtain the visual quality of units, values of landform and land use-cover were combined by a matrix. Motorway sectors were defined by overlapping motorway alternatives over the map of visual quality previously obtained. These sectors were used to measure the magnitude of impacts.

The analysis of the visibility of the new structure was based on the identification of significant viewing points in the motorway sectors described above. The visibility has been expressed as “area from which the structure would be visible” and “population or potential viewers of the new structure”. A single value was obtained for motorway sectors identified (corresponding to integrated landscape units) by averaging the values for all points contained in each sector. The values obtained correspond to “total area from which some point of the new motorway would be visible” and “average viewing area and population for any sector of the motorway”. A combined expression of the area from which a point or sector is visible and the number of viewers is provided by the product between both values and it was used as a measure of the magnitude of impacts.

Intensity has been considered to be directly related to the visual quality of units affected and it was expressed as a correction factor to be applied to

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the magnitude value obtained, in order to have an integrated assessment of visual impact including both magnitude and intensity.

Geomorphologic performance was obtained using the size ratio between the new landform created and the size of natural and the size of the new structure has been expressed as area of the average vertical section and compared with relevant natural linear landforms, be it positive or negative. It is not unreasonable to assume that the lower those values the more "sustainable" the new project would be from the point of view of preserving the visual heritage of the area.

Relevance of impacts was established by comparison with well-known examples of visual landmarks in the region, especially cases which might have been subject to specific visual enhancement actions. This could help to determine the social importance of the impact and the expense local society would be willing to accept its mitigation. For the assessment of relevance, two large buildings were analysed in the main towns in the study area and compared with new structure.

Mitigation measures have been proposed. They should include visual barriers to reduce visibility and contrast between the new structure and the environment; this can be achieved through choice of materials, design details, paint and vegetation.

A methodological approach to assess the impacts of a motorway on visual landscape.

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Introduction

A motorway represents a visual intrusion that may reduce visual quality. This reduction or "visual impact" is related to the degree of visibility of the structure (magnitude) and to the contrast between the structure and pre-existing landscape (intensity). Visual impact assessment has been carried out by analyzing and integrating both magnitude and intensity. The visual quality (intrinsic merit of a unit from a perceptual point of view) and fragility (sensitivity to visual intrusion from human activities) of landscape is determined mainly by three groups of factors: **geomorphology** (relief, shape, rock type); **vegetation and land use** (especially presence of impacting elements such as prominent constructions). The method has been applied to a new motorway between Vitoria and Eibar in the Basque Country, Spain. Key issues in the assessment process are briefly discussed.

Geomorphologic performance:

Criteria applied are ratio between the size of the new landform created and the size of natural, linear landforms in the area. Percent of the study area from which the new structure will be seen can also be used. It is not unreasonable to assume that the lower those values the more "sustainable" the new project would be from the point of view of preserving the visual heritage of the area.

Relevance of impacts:

It is established by comparison with well-known examples of visual landmarks in the region. This could help to determine the social importance of the impact and the expense local society would be willing to accept to mitigate it.

Data needs:

DEM; map of integrated environmental units; geomorphological map; land cover-use map; roads and built-up areas; population data; relevant visual landmarks as standards for comparison.

Operating procedure

The analysis of visual impact has been based on the identification of integrated environmental units defined on the basis of geomorphologic, land cover and human occupation (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Integrated landscape units

The intrinsic visual quality of those units has been determined according to the following procedure and criteria:

- 1) Ranks of visual quality were established for the two components considered in the former units (Tables 1a, 1b).
- 2) Landform and land cover were combined to define visual quality as shown in Table 2.

Table 1a. Categories of visual quality for land use-cover units.

ID	Land use-cover unit	Visual quality
05	Urban areas	1
06	Industrial	1
08	Cultivated prairies and crops with hedges	2
10	Terraced crops and cultivated prairies	2
13	Shrubs	4
15	Rock	4
19	Afforestations	3
20	Deciduous forests	5
23	Crops / afforestations mosaic	3
24	Crops / forest mosaic	4
25	Forests / afforestations mosaic	4
26	Mixed forests / shrubs mosaic	5

Table 1b. Categories of visual quality for landform units.

ID	Landform unit	Visual quality
02	Alluvial plain	1
03	Valley floor and adjacent slope	2
10	Valley slopes and gentle interfluvies	3
11	Abrupt summits and crests	4
12	Network of small valleys and interfluvies	5

Table 2. Matrix of visual quality values obtained by the combination of landform (M) and land cover-use (V-H) values.

V-H \ M	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	1	2	2	3
2	1	2	2	3	3
3	2	2	3	3	4
4	2	3	3	4	5
5	3	3	4	4	5

- 3) Motorway sectors were defined overlapping motorway alternatives and visual quality map (Figure 2). These sectors were used to measure the magnitude of impacts.

Fig. 2. Overlap of motorway alternatives and visual quality units.

Visibility analysis

Significant viewing points in the motorway sectors were used to determine visibility. Visibility was expressed as "area from which the structure would be visible" and "population or potential viewers of the new structure". A single value was obtained for motorway sectors identified by averaging the values for all points contained in each sector. Visibility thus obtained should therefore be interpreted as "maximum visibility". Figures 3a, 3b and Table 3 represent visibility for the two alternatives analysed.

Table 3. Visibility of motorway alternatives

		A	B
VISIBILITY AREA km ²	Total	41.29	82.29
	Sectors' sum*	100.43	322.40
	Sectors' average	8.37	26.87
VIEWING POPULATION pop.	Total	2,736	4,124
	Sectors' sum*	3,287	14,951
	Sectors' average	318	1,245
COMBINED VISIBILITY km ² × pop.	Total	112,969	339,363
	Sectors' average	2,661	33,453

* Sum of visibility areas or viewing population for all motorway sectors, regardless of overlaps.

A combined expression of the area from which a point or sector is visible and the number of viewers is provided by the product between both values. (Table 3).

Impact assessment

Visibility area/population are used as a measure of the **magnitude** of impacts. **Intensity** was directly related to the visual quality of units affected and it was expressed as a correction factor (Figure 4) to be applied to the magnitude value obtained, in order to have an integrated assessment of visual impact including both magnitude and intensity. Table 4 shows impact values obtained using this procedure; Alternative B clearly has the greatest visual impact.

Fig. 4. Relationship between visual quality of units and correction factor applied to magnitude values.

		A	B
VISIBILITY AREA km ²	Quality-corrected sectors' sum	45.24	172.94
	Quality-corrected sectors' average	3.77	14.41
VIEWING POPULATION pop.	Quality-corrected sectors' sum	1,692	7,452
	Quality-corrected sectors' average	141	621
COMBINED IMPACT (km ² × pop.)	Sum	76,546	1,288,749
	Sectors' average	532	8,949

Table 4. Visual impact of motorway alternatives.

Landform modification could thus be considered as acceptable in the case of alternative A, but not for alternative B.

An assessment of relevance has been made by comparison with the visibility of two large structures (buildings) in the area (Figure 5). Visibility of both points is quite similar; the average has been used for comparison (Table 5).

Visibility ratios (Rv) were obtained for those visual landmarks, using both "average sector visibility area", and "average sector viewing population". Area visibility of the reference points considered (point 1) is similar to average area visibility of sectors in the case of alternative A. Population visibility of this alternative is much lower. Alternative B has much higher area visibility than the reference point, and slightly lower population visibility.

Table 5. Visibility of structures used for comparison

Visibility point	Area (km ²)	Population (persons)	Combined visibility (km ² × persons)
1 (Eibar)	8.34	1,898	15,829
2 (Vergara)	10.4	1,419	14,758
Average 1 - 2	9.37	1,659	15,294

A synoptic comparison is provided by combined area × population values. Visibility ratios (Rv) have been obtained.

$$Rv = \frac{\text{Combined impact motorway alternative}}{\text{Average combined visibility standards}}$$

$$Rv_A = 532 / 15,295 = 0.03;$$

$$Rv_B = 8,949 / 15,294 = 0.59;$$

Thus alternative B represents a more significant departure from existing conditions than alternative A.

Fig. 5. Visual landscape: reference points.

Final comments

The results obtained show that the combined average visibility of any motorway sector is considerably lower than the reference value (standard) in the case of alternative A, but more than twice as great for alternative B. That is, this alternative would imply the introduction of an artificial structure much more intrusive from the visual point of view than existing structures in the study area. If the quality corrected values (impacts) are considered, visual intrusion would be lower, equivalent to about half the combined visibility of the reference structure for alternative B and less than 5% for alternative A. Mitigation measures to reduce visual impact should include visual barriers to reduce visibility (vegetation, "naturalised" earth accumulations, etc) and contrast between the new structure (landforms, shapes, colours, textures) and the environment. Compensation through the elimination of "eyesores" in the area (derelict land or structures, spoil heaps, etc) during the period of construction is another possibility.

The method described allows the assessment of impacts using units with specific, measurable magnitudes, thus ensuring replicability of results and reducing subjectivity.

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The use of spatial-temporal landslide data sets for hazard modelling

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Landslide hazard maps are an important tool for the design of mitigation strategies and plans, providing the basis for a better knowledge of natural processes as well as decision-making. In the last three decades, several methodological approaches based on probabilistic landslide hazard assessment have been developed. In this way, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has opened new possibilities in spatial data analysis (SDA), providing the basis for the development, improvement and application of these techniques to landslide hazard zoning. Nevertheless, as the maps obtained are normally not independently validated, they must be considered, from the scientific point of view, as un-tested hypotheses.

This work is a contribution to the development and validation of procedures for landslide hazard analysis, based on the knowledge of both spatial and temporal occurrence of former landslides, through the application of GIS and SDA techniques.

The working hypothesis is that the correlation between landslides occurred in the past and a series of spatial parameters provides the means to predict the future behaviour of this process and express it by means of maps that reflect the spatial and/or spatio-temporal probability of future occurrences.

The work carried out included data gathering on nineteen parameters, selected on the basis of a given rupture model, and the formation of a digital database. The database included rupture zones of past landslides and a series of geometrical, geomorphological, geological, hydrological and land-use data. To develop the models and test the hypothesis, a detailed analysis of landslides occurred in a study area in northern Spain during a period of about forty years has been carried out, considering both spatial and temporal distribution. This analysis was based on field surveys and interpretation of air photographs from eight different flights, at similar

scales, obtained between 1954 and 1997; seven spatial-temporal landslide data sets were thus obtained.

Statistical spatial probability analyses were carried out using two types of mathematical procedures: multivariate analysis (discriminant function) and favorability functions based on both probability and fuzzy set theory.

The results obtained have been independently validated, using different samples for model development and model validation. A temporal validation strategy has been applied, using different temporal landslide sets; this strategy seems to be the most suitable to know the predictive capability of a model. This validation has been used to establish the predictive capability of the model in time, but also to improve the model by means of identifying the most appropriate combination of variables and the most suitable procedure. The predictive value of each unit in the model thus obtained permit to express those units in terms of spatial-temporal probability; that is a hazard map (although only for ruptures).

The temporal analysis has been also used to establish the frequency of landslide occurrence during the period studied. Since there is general trend towards the increase in time of landslide frequency, scenarios for future behaviour must consider this aspect.

The use of spatial-temporal landslide data sets for hazard modelling

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Introduction

Landslide hazard maps are an important tool for the design of mitigation strategies and plans, providing the basis for a better knowledge of natural processes as well as decision-making. In the last three decades, several methodological approaches based on probabilistic landslide hazard assessment have been developed. In this way, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has opened new possibilities in spatial data analysis (SDA), providing the basis for the development, improvement and application of these techniques to landslide hazard zoning. Nevertheless, as the maps obtained are normally not independently validated, they must be considered, from the scientific point of view, as un-tested hypotheses.

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Figure 1. Location of the Deva municipality.

The work carried out was based on the selection of a given rupture model (Figure 2), and the formation of a digital database including rupture zones of past landslides and a series of geometrical, geomorphological, geological, hydrological and land-use data (Table 1). To develop the models and test the hypothesis, a detailed analysis of landslides occurred in the study area (Figure 1) during a period of about forty years has been carried out, considering both spatial and temporal distribution. This analysis was based on field surveys and interpretation of air photographs from eight different flights, at similar scales, obtained between 1954 and 1997; seven spatial-temporal landslide data sets were thus obtained (Figure 3).

Variable	Description
Location of failure zone	
Mass movements (MOVPT)	Represents shallow landslides used in the analysis.
DEM	
Elevation (DEM)	Altitude asl, in meters.
Terrain geometry	
Slope gradient (PEND)	Slope gradient at failure zone, in degrees.
Aspect (ORIENT)	Slope aspect, eight classes, 45° each.
Insolation (INSOL)	Maximum solar radiation on March, 21.
Roughness (RUGOS)	Divergence of vectors normal to pixel surface within 3 x 3 pixels window.
Curvature perpendicular to slope (PLA)	Degree of concavity/convexity along a line perpendicular to slope profile.
Curvature along slope gradient (PERFIL)	Degree of concavity/convexity of the slope profile.
General curvature (CURVAR)	Degree of 3D concavity/convexity of the slope.
Regolith thickness (GROSOR)	Thickness of surface deposits.
Hydrological variables	
Upstream area (ACUENCA)	Area of upstream drainage basin.
Basin length (LONG)	Upstream basin length.
Upstream surface deposit area (AFS)	Upstream basin area with surface deposit.
Upstream surface deposit length (LFS)	Length of upstream area with surface deposit.
Average slope gradient (PENDM)	Average slope gradient of the upstream basin.
Land-use	
Vegetation (VEGET)	Land cover type and density.
Lithology	
Lithology (LITO)	Bedrock and surface deposit.

Table 1. Variables considered.

Figure 2. The principal type of movement corresponds to debris slides/flows, affecting weathered and colluvial materials. Rupture surfaces develop at the contact between regolith and bedrock, usually parallel to the land surface. The geometrical characteristics of the slope are a crucial landslide conditioning factor as far as water concentration capacity is concerned. The steep gradient of slopes, often verging on the limits of stability, is responsible for surface formations being highly sensitive to small changes in cohesion or in pore water pressure. Vegetation is important for soil infiltration capacity and its humidity, as well as soil cohesion. Lithology is another important factor that controls cohesion.

Figure 3. Spatio-temporal landslide data sets.

Figure 4. Methodological flow-chart diagram.

Statistical spatial probability analyses (Figure 4) were carried out using different Favourability Functions (Chung and Fabbri, 1993) based on both probability and fuzzy set theory.

Correlation between past landslides and conditioning factors was used to obtain models representing susceptibility to new ruptures (Figure 5).

The steps for applying the model are: 1) creation of unique condition sub-areas by overlay of all thematic layers (Chung et al., 1995); 2) estimation of favourability values by means of bivariate relationships between mapped past movements and individual thematic layers, thereby obtaining susceptibility values for every variable under consideration; 3) integration of favourability values at each unique condition sub-area using a specific Favourability Function; 4) re-classification of all values into 200 susceptibility classes (each one corresponding to 0.5% of the study area).

Calculated values must be considered solely as estimators of future behaviour (the closer the value in a pixel to the maximum theoretical value of the function, the more likely the occurrence of future landslides in that pixel).

Figure 5. Landslide susceptibility model obtained using the Certainty Factor function, considering elevation, aspect, slope gradient, lithology and vegetation. The 200 Susceptibility classes are represented in pseudo-color.

Figure 6. Validation of different models (the greater the departure from the diagonal the better the model).

Figure 7. Validation using different time periods.

The results obtained have been independently validated, using different samples for model development and model validation. A temporal validation strategy has been applied, using different temporal landslide sets; this strategy seems to be the most suitable to know the predictive capability of a model. This validation has been used to establish the predictive capability of the model in time, and also to improve the model by means of identifying the most appropriate combination of variables and the most suitable procedure.

Figure 6 shows that a model based on only 5 variables (elevation, aspect, slope gradient, lithology and vegetation) provides the best balance between data or effort requirement and precision of the model. Figure 7 indicates that model capability to predict future behaviour is essentially constant in time. That is the underlying hypothesis of "uniformitarian behaviour" appears to be correct.

Susceptibility class	% landslides in class	Corrected % (fit)	Prob. A (50 years)	Prob. B (50 years)	Prob. C (50 years)
200	4	3.314	0.00685	0.03598	0.05336
199	2.5	2.869	0.00593	0.03115	0.04620
198	2.4	2.609	0.00539	0.02833	0.04202
197	5	2.425	0.00501	0.02633	0.03905
196	2.2	2.281	0.00472	0.02477	0.03674
195	0.7	2.165	0.00447	0.02350	0.03486
...
176	0.5	1.249	0.00258	0.01356	0.02012
175	0.7	1.224	0.00253	0.01329	0.01971
...
150	0.5	0.805	0.00166	0.00874	0.01296
...
125	0.2	0.536	0.00111	0.00582	0.00864
...
101	0.2	0.360	0.00074	0.00391	0.00580
100	0.2	0.354	0.00073	0.00384	0.00570
99	0.5	0.348	0.00072	0.00377	0.00560
...
55	0.2	0.118	0.00024	0.00128	0.00189
...
28	0.2	0.009	0.00002	0.00010	0.00014
...
10	0.3	0.000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
...
1	0.0	0.000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000

Table 2. Numerical expression of graphs in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Three scenarios for future landslide occurrence.
A) Total No. Of landslides in next 50 years equal to past 50 years.
B) No. Of landslides per year in the future equivalent to last 5 years.
C) No. Of landslides increasing yearly according to past trend.

The predictive value of the model thus obtained makes it possible to transform susceptibility (spatial probability) classes into hazard (spatio-temporal probability) ones.

Frequency of past landslide occurrence can be determined through temporal analysis. Since there is general trend towards the increase of landslide frequency with time, scenarios for future behaviour can be defined (Figure 8). Susceptibility models can thus be transformed into different hazard models (one for each scenario considered). Table 2 shows the equivalence between susceptibility and hazard classes.

Conclusions

- Susceptibility models obtained with the method described represent useful forecasts of future behaviour, not perfect but with known, independently tested predictive validity.
- Probability of occurrence based on temporal analysis of past landslides provides the basis to transform susceptibility into hazard maps.
- Realistic scenarios, based on past evolution of the process, can be considered to derived different hazard models.
- The method represents a useful basis for the elaboration of quantitative risk maps (damages).

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